

Students perspective on Online Learning and Contact Learning during Pandemic Situation

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Abstract - 'Covid-19', the pandemic threat on one side and the lockdown on the other side shattered the lives of majority human beings on the planet. It brought in numerous problems and caused devastation beyond the imagination of anyone. The survival itself has become the most difficult and problematic to the majority of the population. Students and teachers are no exception to this situation. The biggest concern to both teachers and students is 'time'. They cannot go out and are home bound due to lockdown. Under these circumstances, to quench the thirst of students to learn and the desire of teachers to teach was met to some extent in the form of online learning and teaching. This paper presents some of the digital tools that assist to cater to the needs of students and teachers along with the survey conducted on regular classwork and e-learning during lockdown period.

Key Words: online learning, online-teaching, lockdown, students and teachers, digital tools

1. INTRODUCTION

Online learning or e-learning are the buzzing words during this pandemic situation among the community of students across the world. Student community in India is no exception. But this is not the case with parents, teachers and Society in the Indian context when it comes to learning. The traditional and conventional teaching was always considered the best both for teachers and students. It is imprinted in the minds of the people of India that students should go to school/college and learn from teachers in the class. Only then, it was assumed that the student has undertaken a course and learning from curriculum. More importantly, teachers emotionally connect with students and quench their thirst of teaching in the face to face interaction. There are many reasons for this impression that students learn better through regular classwork going to school/college. One reason, among the them, the success of the students both in personal life and professional career. All this is fine before the Covid-19 pandemic situation. Indian tradition and culture of teaching-learning process got good name as our students excelled across the world.

Suddenly, like a bolt from the blue, corona virus started spreading across the world and got the nomenclature 'Covid-19'. India is no exception to this pandemic as the travel across the world is a piece of cake for the many. This

resulted to challenging times both for the people and to the Government. As the Government has announced lockdown to prevent spread of virus on a large scale, it benefitted both parents and children in getting a rare opportunity of spending some time together along with various concerns of 'life', such as survival with health and future prosperity. Among the many concerns that Corona posed to the world, one important concern is education of the children/student community. Every challenging situation throw an opportunity for those who are persuasive. Teachers and students found the way out with the help of various web tools readily available for the various purposes. Thus, a new era of e-learning has become way of life from now on. Of the various tools available, some of the tools that are prominent and are used across the world are given hereunder.

2. ONLINE RESOURCES TO TEACH

There are many web tools for online teaching and meetings. Of these, some web tools which are widely known to many and offering free services(with limitations) to people in general are Google Meet, Zoom, Cisco Webex, Microsoft Teams. Some of the important features of these web tools are:

Google Meet: Some of its features include unlimited number of meetings, Live captioning during meetings, compatible across devices, Video and audio preview screen, adjustable layouts and screen settings, importantly controls for meeting hosts, screen sharing with participants, messaging with participants, and Integrating with google and Microsoft Office apps, etc.,

Zoom: Some of its features include join from anywhere on any device, Access robust security solutions throughout, built-in tools for screen sharing, HD Video and audio calling, built-in recording and transcripts, support for up to 1000 video participants, etc.,

Cisco Webex: Some of its features include video and audio web conferencing, easy to start, schedule, and can accommodate up to 3000 attendees in the meet, etc.,

Microsoft Teams: Some of its features include fully integrated with Office 365, direct access to email, one drive, share point, Skype, access across all devices, collaborate

securely, conversation threads, cyber security, new grid view, etc.,

3. PARADIGM SHIFT IN TEACHING

In view of the lockdown, teachers are forced to adopt online teaching. It is very difficult for teachers to move from face to face interaction to teach online as they normally get connected to students emotionally while teaching. Yet, as teachers teach every day to face the challenges and make the challenges into opportunities, they got the opportunity to put these teachings into practice, and quickly adopted to online teaching as per the software tools suggested by the authorities of the college. Whereas, students are more tech savvy and could switch to online learning as they have huge exposure to online mode. This tendency of students paved the opportunity to collect some data with regarding to online teaching and learning as they are the main stake holders of the process.

4. SURVEY ON ONLINE TEACHING VS CONTACT TEACHING:

The following questionnaire along with options to choose is prepared to collect the data from students with regard to Online Teaching. Though students have exposure to internet, only a few were truly adopting online learning. The questions and the options to answer the questions are:

1. Your view on contact learning before lockdown:

a) The only option b) Not heard of online learning c) contact learning and home work is fine d) contact learning should be supported with online learning e) other _____

2. Your view on online learning before lockdown:

a) No idea b) No equipment c) No exposure to online learning d) Not tried online learning e) other _____

3. Your view on online learning during lockdown:

a) Not helpful. Audio and Video issues. b) online learning with contact learning is good c) online learning with homework(reading/writing) is fine d) online learning is fine e) other _____

4. Your view on contact learning during second term of lockdown:

a) The best b) Contact learning should be supplemented with online learning c) contact learning with homework (reading and writing) is fine d) online learning is fine e) other _____

5. Your view on online learning during second term of lockdown:

a) The best b) online learning should be supplemented with contact learning c) online learning with homework is fine d) online learning is fine e) other _____

5. SURVEY ANALYSIS

In the survey, the first question was put to enquire about their view on contact learning before the lockdown. The following pie chart presents the views of the students about contact learning as follows:

1) Your view on Contact Learning before lock down. 30 responses

Students are suddenly forced to be home bound in view of the lockdown and pandemic situation. The students who have gone through regular classwork throughout their schooling and junior college for a minimum of 12 years expressed that the learning process is complete as discussed hereunder:

- 40% of students have voted for Contact learning i.e., regular classwork with face to face interaction along with homework is fine. Whereas,
- 36.7% of students have expressed that Contact learning i.e., regular classwork with face to face interaction should be supported with online teaching, in a way they do not know the terminology but are opting for blended learning.
- 13.3% of students shared that there is no other choice than to migrate to online learning. Surprisingly,
- 10% of students are not heard of online learning at all.

Moving forward, the second question posed to the students is to find out their views on online learning before lockdown. The following is the pie chart that presents the views of the students.

2) Your view on 'online' Learning before lock down. 30 responses

Students though have exposure to online tools such as Whatsapp, Facebook, and might have heard of education related stuff such as videos online, e-books and online courses but as far as getting educated through online mode only is beyond their perception in general. The above pie chart shares the response of the students as follows:

- 46.7% of students shares that they have not tried that education/learning completely online and could not think of before the lockdown.
- 20% of students confessed clearly that they do not have any exposure to online learning of any sort.
- surprisingly, 16.7% of students clearly expressed that they do not have any idea with regard to online learning, and
- there are students in small chunks feel that either they do not want to try it or feel not possible to learn online.

5.1 LOCKDOWN EXPERIENCES

Learning not just happens on college campus and in class, but students learn a lot by throwing themselves to various situations. They attend classes, meet friends, discuss in canteen, chat on net (whatsapp, facebook, Instagram, etc.,). Students learn from all these experiences. One experience they have not heard of and could not imagine is lockdown and homebound because of the pandemic. Therefore, they are asked to share their views on learning online during lockdown. The following pie chart shows the responses of the students:

3) Your view on 'online' Learning during lock down.

30 responses

- 30% of students feel online learning with homework (reading/writing) is fine.
- 26.7% of students feel online learning is fine.
- 20% of students feel online learning not helpful, there are hurdles such as audio and video issues.
- 16.7% of students feel online learning with contact learning is good.
- some students feel that network issues cannot help them to access online learning and some students feel that finding it difficult to focus for long duration as this is a new medium to learn.

4) Your view on 'Contact Learning' during second term of lock down.

30 responses

- 43.3% of students feel contact learning should be supplemented with online learning
- 26.7% of students feel online learning is fine
- 19.7% of students feel contact learning with homework (reading / writing) is fine
- some minor part of the students feel contact learning is good and the best option and some students expressed it is not possible to have contact learning now.

The following is the response to the final and last question asked to share their views on online learning during second term of lock down is as follows in the pie chart:

5) Your view on 'online' Learning during second term of lock down.

30 responses

- 36.7% of students feel online learning is fine
- 23.3% of students feel online learning should be supplemented with contact learning
- 16.7% of students feel online learning with homework (reading / writing) is fine

There are some students who feel online learning is best, but some have hurdles such as audio and video disturbances, internet work issues, etc.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the survey, it is observed that teachers shifted to online teaching to fulfil their desire to teach and to meet the obligation/requirements. Though students are tech savvy, yet students are not completely ready for Online learning. It is a typical experience to the students to focus and be active during online learning for long periods of time. Majority of the student community have lot of exposure to internet, yet they are not ready for online learning completely as they love interaction with teachers, friends and college life. On the

whole, 80% of the students who wanted to have contact learning alone before the lockdown slowly digested the realities of life such as possibility of spread of corona virus. They felt that waiting and being homebound is a good way to fight corona virus, made them change their opinion. They shared after two lockdowns that online learning is fine and should be supplemented with homework (reading / writing) and interaction with faculty.

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BIOGRAPHIES

Venata Ramana Kolluru with 13 years of teaching experience in English to undergraduate engineering students and also taught subjects such as Professional Ethics, Constitution of India, Gender Sensitization Lab.